

Nepal Sanskrit University

One-Year B. Ed. Compulsory Course Foundation of Education

Course No. : Ed. 3001

Nature of the course: Theoretical

Full Marks 35

Course Duration.... 150 hrs

Number of Periods ... 180

Periods per week :6

Time per period 50 min

Course Description:

This course on education is for One-Year B. Ed. programme. This course is designed to provide the students with basic background of Foundations of Education. It contains eight units with part one and two: Part one ten contains concepts of education and curriculum. Philosophical and sociological foundations, concepts of teaching with its various methods and modern trends of education. part two contains overview of development of Nepalese education with some government efforts in education development and some problems and issues in school system.

General Objective:

- This course aims at helping students conceptualize the meaning of education and curriculum, philosophical and sociological aspects, teaching methods and develop understanding of Nepalese education system.

Specific objectives:

On the completion of this course the students will be able to -

- define education and curriculum
- define the western philosophical thoughts with their implications to education,
- explain the concepts of educational sociology,
- explain the concepts of teaching.
- list the qualities of a good teacher,
- analyze and interpret the alternative approaches to education
- describe development trend of Nepalese education,

- 2.3.4 Evaluation of learning outcomes
- 2.4 Foundations of curriculum
(Philosophical, Sociological, Psychological and Humanistic foundations)
- 2.5 Importance of co-curricular and extra-curricular activities in education
- 2.6 Curriculum materials
(Text book, Teachers' guide, Teaching unit, Instructional materials)

Unit-3 Philosophical Foundation

- 3.1 Meaning of philosophy and its implications to education
- 3.2 Schools of philosophy
(Idealism, Naturalism, Pragmatism with reference to objectives curriculum, educative process, teachers' role and students' role)

Unit-4 Sociological Foundation

- 4.1 Meaning of sociology of education
- 4.2 Concept of society and community
- 4.3 Relation between school and community
- 4.4 Education as a process of socialization
(Meaning and Process)
- 4.5 Modes of socialization
(Meaning of socialization-Repressive and Permissive modes)
- 4.6 Patterns of social interaction
(Meaning of social interaction and its' implications to the class room)
- 4.7 Agencies of socialization
(Meaning of social groups-Family, School, Community, Peer group and Association)

Unit-5 Psychological Foundation

- 5.1 Concept of psychological foundations
- 5.2 Learners' educational needs
- 5.3 Individual differences
- 5.4 Learning behaviour

Unit-6 Concept of Teaching

- 6.1 Meaning of teaching

- 6.2 Phases of teaching
(Pre-active, Interactive, Post-active)
- 6.3 Qualities of a good teacher
- 6.4 Creating educational environment in the classroom
- 6.5 Role of headmaster
- 6.6 Role of headmaster as a supervisor

Unit-7 Methods of Teaching

- 7.1 Lecture/Exposition method
- 7.2 Discussion method
- 7.3 Project method
- 7.4 problem solving method
(with reference to concept, use, and limitations)

Unit-8 Modern Trends in Education

- 8.1 Equal opportunity in education
- 8.2 Education for human resource development
- 8.3 Education for All
- 8.4 Role of politics in education
- 8.5 Education for international understanding and development of humanity
- 8.6 Alternative approaches to education
 - 8.6.1 Non-formal education
 - 8.6.2 Open learning
- 8.6. Continuing education

Part Two

Education in Nepal

Unit-9 Education in Nepal

- 9.1 Education development before democracy (before 2007 B.S.)
- 9.2 Education development after democracy (after 2007 B.S.)
- 9.3 Recommendations of major educational plan and commission reports (NNEPC 1954, NESP 1971, NEC 1992, HLNEC 1998)
- 9.4 Present status of school education in Nepal
(National objectives, level wise objectives, curriculum, structure and evaluation)

- 9.5 Curriculum development process in Nepal
- 9.6 Government's efforts in education - BPEP, SEDP

Unit-10 Problems and Issues of School Education in Nepal

- 10.1 Structural problems issues
- 10.2 Policy problems/issues
- 10.3 Equity and access problems/issues
- 10.4 Quality and relevancy problems issues
- 10.5 Vocational and technical problems/issues

Instructional Techniques:

- Discussion and demonstration
- Lecture/exposition and explanation
- Use of resource persons
- Individual and group work, project work
- Library study

Assessment Techniques and Mark Distribution

- Written examination - 100 marks
- Unit wise mark distribution
 - Part one - 70 marks
 - Unit two-30 marks

Question wise mark distribution

- | | |
|----------------------------------|-----------------|
| 20 multiple - choice questions - | 20×1 = 20 marks |
| 2 - long answer questions | 12×2 = 24 marks |
| 8 short answer questions | 8×7 = 56 marks |

References

1. Brubacher, John S. (1978) *Modern Philosophies of Education* New Delhi: McGraw Hill, Publishing Company.
2. Chaube, S.P. and A. Chaube (1994) *Fondations of Educaton*, New Delhi: Vikas Publishing House.
3. Das, B.N.(1994) *Foundation of Educational Thought and Practice* Calcutta: Kalyani Publishers.
4. Faber, Charles F. and Gilbert F. Shearron (1970) *Elementary School Administration* (Theory and practice) New York/Sydney, Holt, Richart and Winston. Inc.
5. Otaway, A.K.C.(1994) *Education and Society: An Introduction to Sociology of Education*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.

- explain the efforts made by the government for the development of education and
- discuss at greater length on the problems and issues of the school education in Nepal.

Course contents:

Part-One

Unit-1	Concept of Education	12 periods
Unit -2	Concepts of Curriculum	25 periods
Unit-3	Philosophical Foundations	30 periods
Unit-4	Sociological Foundations	25 periods
Unit-5	Psychological Foundations	5 periods
Unit-6	Concept of Teaching	15 periods
Unit-7	Methods of Teaching	13 periods
Unit-8	Modern Trends of Education	20 periods

Part-Two

Unit-9	Education in Nepal	25 periods
Unit-10	Problems and Issues of school Education in Nepal	<u>10 periods</u>
Total 180 periods		

Course content in detail:

Part-One

Unit-1	Concept of Education
	1.1 Meaning and definitions of education
	1.2 Aims of education
	1.3 Social, economical and political role of education
	1.4 Forms of education
Unit-2	Concept of Curriculum
	2.1 Meaning and definitions of curriculum
	2.2 Difference between curriculum and course of study
	2.3 Basic elements of curriculum
	2.3.1 Objectives
	(Sources of objectives. Taxonomy of objectives)
	2.3.2 Contents
	(Selection and Organization of learning experiences)
	2.3.3 Methods
	(Teacher-centered and Student centered)

6. Sharma, R.N.(1992) *Philosophy and Sociology and Education* Delhi: Surjeet Publications.
7. Saxena, N.R.(1993) *Philosophical and Sociological Foundation of Education*, Meerut: Vinaya Rakheja for Surya Publication.
8. Tyler, Rallph W. (1967) *Basic Principles of Curriculum and Instruction*. The University of Chicago Press.
9. Aryal, K.R. (1970) *Education for the Development of Nepal* Kathmandu: Nepal Shanti Prakashan.
10. Bista, M.B. (2043) *Shikshya Ko Siddhanta*, Kathmandu: Shijha Prakashan.
11. Dhakal, M.P. (2058 4th ed.) *Philosophical and Sociological Foundations of Education*. Kathmandu; Bidhyarthi Pustak Bhandar
12. HLNEC (1998) *High Level Education Commission Report*, Kathmandu.
13. Nepalma Shikshya (1954) *Nepal National Education Planning Commission (NNEPC) Nepal*: College of Education.
14. NESP (1971) *National Educational System Plan*. Kathmandu: HMG/Ministry of Education.
15. NEC (1992) *National Education Commission Report Kathmandu*.
16. Pradhan. Kedar (ed.) (2055) *Philosophical and Sociological Foundation of Education*. Lalitpur: Nepal: Lalit Shikshaya Campus.
17. Wagle, M. P. (1994) *foundations of Education*. Bhotahity, Kathmandu: Ganesh Himal Education.